

FATIGUE DESIGN OF CAST ALUMINIUM PASSENGER CAR WHEELS WITH RESPECT TO THE TRANSFER OF CYCLIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES

M. Hell¹

Wheels of passenger cars combine aesthetic and aerodynamic aspects and are crucial for vehicle dynamics and safety. Driven by the vehicle design and the vehicle dynamics, especially the huge weight of electric vehicles, tire widths and wheel sizes increase steadily while weight targets are lowered at the same time. Looking at the sheer numbers of produced wheels around the globe, the impact of weight reductions on energy consumption and emissions for production and vehicle usage are obvious. Weight optimisations of the wheel require design iterations which entail large number of fatigue life and manufacturing simulations. The applied models have to be simple enough to be manageable in everyday practice and complex enough to capture all relevant influencing factors. The paper therefore presents an advanced Weakest Link Approach which extends the original formulation by a localised material behaviour. It allows the consideration of manufacturing influences and inhomogeneous property distributions. The parametrisation of the approach can be based on material testing with specimens as well as knowledge from prior component testing. The application of the approach reduces uncertainties in the fatigue estimation and allows an increase in material utilisation without diminishing safety margins.

Keywords: Numerical Fatigue Assessment, Size Effects, Component Strength, Damage Accumulation

CHALLENGES FOR FATIGUE ESTIMATION AND COMPONENT OPTIMISATION

Modern, complex wheel designs differ a lot from classical periodic and symmetrical radial spoke or mesh designs. Stress concentrations result from loading gradients (bending and torsion) and the component geometry. Depending on the design, a fully three-dimensional stress-strain state beneath the surface is present already during uniaxial loading and even simple cyclic load cases may lead to rotations in principal stress direction. In case of unfavourably oriented anisotropic microstructures, this effect may lead to an additional reduction in fatigue performance, as discussed by Scurria et al. [1]. Moreover, usual service load time functions contain overloads or misuse maneuvers, which could provoke locally limited plasticity, even if no structural yielding occurs. Figure 1 shows the result for the simulation of a revolving biaxial load from ZWARP testing. The load case (maximum load case cornering) results in an excess of the yield limit in a wider area on the spoke in-line with the radial

1) RONAL GmbH, Karl-Wirth-Strasse 100, 76694 Forst, Germany, matthias.hell@ronalgroup.com

force and different locally confined plastic zones at the transition of spoke to hub and at the radii of the window between the spokes.

FIGURE 1 Local stress response to simple biaxial loading

Load spectra for passenger car wheels and other safety critical components are usually scaled up in order to reduce testing times. This aggravates the challenge of describing the actual stress-strain state, which is preliminary for a sufficiently accurate fatigue life estimation and a consequent lightweight design optimisation. The locally limited plasticity depends on the remaining elastic cross section, which defines the boundary conditions for the cyclic deformation. In this case, the local elasto-plastic stress-strain path can only be described correctly, if the material model is suitable for an evaluation of the local strain response and the resulting shift of mean stresses by localised plastic straining. The strain-life approach allows the usage of arbitrarily complex material models and provides a strain-life relation applicable to the LCF as well as to the HCF regime. At the same time, the number of experiments, required for the definition of the material and fatigue behaviour is severely reduced in comparison with the nominal stress approach, if the data from the fatigue and component testing is exploited thoroughly.

STATE OF THE ART FATIGUE ASSESSMENT FOR CAST ALUMINIUM WHEELS

In most cases a practical and simple nominal stress approach will be applied on basis of a material S-N curve and different correction factors. Ramamurty Raju et al. [2] evaluate the fatigue life based on numerical simulations for the cornering fatigue test and fatigue data from rotary bending tests with specimens extracted from the spoke of the wheel. Size and mean stress effects are not considered. Wang et al. [3] apply a nominal stress approach with different correction factors for component size and notch effects. Li et al. [4] describe a through process modelling approach, which estimates residual stresses and microstructures based on the process parameters.

Other work without limitation to the application for wheel fatigue analysis frequently focusses on the role of defects, especially pores. A good comprehensive overview over influencing factors on fatigue behaviour of A356 and possible practical approaches to deal with the influence of mean stresses, defects and component size is presented by Nourian-Avval and Fatemi [5]. The influence of defects and the statistical size effect is treated with the Kitagawa-Takahashi Diagram and the El-

Haddad criterion for the intrinsic crack size. The approach shows good results for specimens also under consideration of the influence of casting surfaces and realistic process routes. In turn, the approach requires a profound characterisation of the defect status, presented by the authors in [6]. In order to estimate fatigue limits for a new component geometry or variable process parameters from a draft, a validated process simulation with a forecast of the defect position and morphology may be required.

The very simple nominal stress approaches are limited with respect to the transfer between components with significant changes in the geometry, the loading or the process parameters, because stress- or material-gradient effects are only considered only by correctional factors. The physically sound models based on fracture mechanics on the other hand yield good results but are in most cases too complex for design iterations with a large number of calculations. Therefore the paper focusses on simple methods in order to implement the influence of material and stress gradients on the fatigue life in order to improve the fatigue life estimation.

INTERACTION BETWEEN MATERIAL, LOADING, GEOMETRY AND MANUFACTURING

The local strain response governs the fatigue performance and is governed by the complex interaction of the loading, the component geometry and the manufacturing related material behaviour and morphology, as Figure 2 illustrates schematically. Nearly all manufacturing steps and processes leave their fingerprint in the material and cause local inhomogeneities and property gradients throughout the component volume.

FIGURE 2 Cross-relations between manufacturing, geometry, material properties, loading and strain response

The manufacturing induced property gradient is superimposed by the stress gradient resulting from the interaction between external loading and component geometry. The strain response of the material to the loading therefore represents a combination of the stress and material gradient. It drives the local fatigue processes starting with a crack nucleation at defects over short crack growth up to stable crack propagation and final structural failure of the wheel. The constant degradation processes, marked by the movement, generation and annihilation of dislocations and dislocation structures, also changes the stress-strain behaviour continuously. A valid evaluation of the strain response requires

the numerical modelling including the influence of defect and property gradients. At the same time, the numerical model has to be efficient and lean enough to be applicable during the draft phase with a large number of optimisation iterations. The proposed modification of the weakest link approach provides an interface for the consideration of loading and material gradients based on the statistical evaluation of the local material behaviour and the manufacturing influence. It allows the transfer of fatigue properties between specimen and component as well as between components with different geometry.

STRAIN-LIFE APPROACH AND TRANSFER METHODS FOR THE CONSIDERATION OF SIZE EFFECTS

In load based linear-elastic approaches the transfer of fatigue properties from the specimen to the component level requires different transfer approaches for the consideration of relevant influencing factors. The influencing factor related to the localised plasticity of notched or inhomogeneous loaded components is described as notch support effect. It is related to the phenomenon, that notched specimens endure a larger number of cycles to failure than the calculated elastic notch stress would suggest on basis of the S-N curve for the un-notched material. It is superimposed by different size effects, which were defined by Kloos as statistical, mechanical, surface related and technological size effect. [7] In the load based linear-elastic approach it is challenging, to experimentally assess or treat those effects separately. The available methods usually represent a superposition of different size and notch support effects. This circumstance limits the transferability to more or less narrow variations of loading scenarios, material gradients and component geometry. The main advantage of the elasto-plastic strain-based approaches in this respect is the possible abstraction between the modelling of the strain response and the treatment of stochastic phenomena.

The fundamental assumption of the classical strain-life approach is the equivalence between the material behaviour of an infinitesimal small volume at the notch root and a homogeneously loaded specimen of the same material. This assumption has to be amended by considerations of different types of size effects. Figure 3 shows a strain-life fatigue approach with interfaces for the consideration of different possible size effects. With the elasto-plastic material behaviour, for example acc. to Ramberg-Osgood, the component geometry and the load-time function, a FE model is set up. From the solution of the model the local stress-strain history as well as correlation measurements (gradients and highly stressed volumina) are obtained. It has to be denoted, that also the extension of highly stressed volumina and the stress gradient explicitly depend on the load-time history. Starting at local peak stresses, the local damage is calculated based on the full σ - ε field data. The spectrum of the local stress-time history is then processed with a local damage accumulation against Damage Parameter P-N curves, which are derived from the strain-life curve and implement the influence of mean stresses on the fatigue performance. The P-N curves are modified by a modification of Weibull's weakest link theory, which accounts for possible deviations in the defect distribution and differences in local fatigue performance.

FIGURE 3 Strain-life approach with interfaces for the consideration of mechanical and statistical size effects

The Mechanical Size Effect I denotes a scale dependency of the material properties. For polycrystalline materials with well dispersed microstructural morphology the material behaves homogeneous, if the length scale of the examined specimen is large with respect to the microstructural lengths (grain size, dendrite arm spacing, etc.) and the specimen is homogeneously loaded. For real life components, this is generally not the case. Manufacturing induced anisotropy and local variations in the microstructure are superimposed by gradients of the stress or strain field. In addition, variable amplitude loading may trigger anisotropic behaviour under certain orientations by rotating directions of the principal stresses. It is necessary, to account for these effects during finite element modelling. Therefore, the local material behaviour has to be assessed either using full field strain measurements or small scale specimens extracted from real life components with comparable manufacturing parameters. In the sense of Kloos' original definition of size effects in linear-elastic approaches, the Mechanical Size Effect I corresponds to the technological size effect.

The Mechanical Size Effect II is strongly related to the extension of the plastic zone relative to the remaining elastic cross section. The deformation boundary conditions of local material depends on the straining of the surrounding material. If the cross section is loaded with a constant stress, the load ratio of the external load is equivalent to the stress-ratio of the local stresses. If, at notches or in the general case of components with complex shape, stress gradients are present, the material yields only locally. If the plastic zone is small compared to the remaining rest cross section, its deformation will be strain-controlled. On unloading after tensional yield, the remaining cross section will induce compressive stresses in the highly stressed material volume. If the yield zone is large compared to the remaining cross section, the residual strains in the yielded volume will induce tensional stresses in the surrounding material. Especially under variable amplitude loading, this effect leads to a pronounced load sequence effect, which is already well established and discussed for fracture mechanics approaches. In order to account for this size effect, it is necessary to evaluate the strain response considering the effects of stress gradients. The external load-time function has to be transferred to the local strain-time function before counting algorithms are applied. Otherwise, changes in mean stresses may be ignored, leading to inaccuracy in the damage accumulation.

The Statistical Size Effect is related to the natural scatter of the fatigue properties. It depends on the dispersion and the morphology of defects. In cast components, the defects, such as, for example,

voids, porosity, segregations, inclusions, depend on the manufacturing parameters and are seldomly distributed homogeneous throughout the material volume. The defect influence can only be described correctly, if the local defect distribution can be assessed with manufacturing simulations or with measurements (x-Ray, tomography etc.). Different approaches have been proposed for the consideration of size effects. A modified Weakest Link Approach is able to capture the local property gradient and differences in defect population.

Experimental Analysis of the Local Cyclic Material Behaviour

For cast aluminium passenger car wheels, AlSi7Mg0,3 alloy (A356), is widely in use. The cyclic material behaviour on the casting process as well as the consecutive heat treatment by solution annealing and artificial ageing. The cyclic material properties and the microstructure show a large dependence on the casting and heat treatment parameters and will be distributed inhomogeneously throughout the material volume. The effect of different microstructures on fatigue for A356 is described, for example, by Houria et al. [8] and in [9,10].

In order to assess the influence of the manufacturing influenced behaviour and to account for material gradients, a extraction schematic as shown in Figure 4 was used. The extraction positions cover the Hub region, the spoke, the transition between spoke, bed and tire seat and the bed/well.

FIGURE 4 Extraction pattern for the experimental examination of the local material and fatigue behaviour

The applied specimen geometry is shown in Figure 5. The specimen blanks were conventionally manufactured from the wheel and then electric discharge machined to the final geometry.

FIGURE 5 Specimen geometry applied for testing

The tests were all executed in strain-control with a Sandner clip-on strain gauge on a ZWICK Rel 2100 Test System with an Instron 8800 Acquisition and Control System, see Figure 6. For tests with high strain amplitude, a buckling support was employed (not visible in the Figure).

FIGURE 6 Test rig, detail of the clamping

From the test results, cyclic deformation curves were derived, in order to assess the cyclic stabilisation and crack initiation cycle numbers. The point of crack initiation is determined recursively from a 5 % drop in the load at the tensional load reversal point, see Figure 7 (left).

FIGURE 7 Cyclic deformation curves (left) and stress-strain path of a fatigue test from Position 1

Figure 8 (left) shows, that cyclic hardening can be observed for all 3 extraction positions. The initial loading curves and the stabilised hystereses differ substantially. The same is true for the stabilised stress-strain curves acc. to Ramberg-Osgood, evaluated at half the number of cycles to crack initiation.

FIGURE 8 Comparison between initial loading curves and stabilised hysteresis for extraction position 1, 2 and 3 (left), cyclically stabilised stress-strain curves acc. to Ramberg Osgood for extraction positions 1-4 (right)

MODIFIED WEAKEST-LINK-APPROACH FOR THE CONSIDERATION OF SIZE EFFECTS AND DEFECT DISTRIBUTIONS

The proposed modifications to the weakest link approach [11, 12] provide different interfaces for knowledge based information, i.e. from prior component testing, as well as for the consideration of manufacturing induced property gradients. It is necessary to discretise the analytical functions and to numerically approximate the volume integrals as sum over the elements in the highly stressed regions, in order to keep the effort manageable. In order to reduce post processing times, the stress function is discretised to average values at the element centre, using the maximum principal stress criterion. The correlation object chosen is the volume. It is also possible and recommended by some authors to correlate survival probabilities with the highly stressed area [13]. Instead of using complicated area formulations it is in this case also possible to select only elements with a boundary surface, if the element resolution is high enough. The following mathematical framework is applicable to arbitrary correlation objects.

The survival probability for a homogeneously loaded Volume V_{ref} with also homogenous material behaviour and defect density is known from experiments and can be described using the Weibull distribution according to Equation 1, where $\sigma_{a,ref}$ denotes the stress amplitude for a survival probability of $P_s=36,8\%$ for a fixed number of cycles to failure and σ_a denotes the loading of the specimen. The shape parameter b_σ as well as $\sigma_{a,ref}$ have to be statistically derived from test data (either specimen or component). In order to estimate the parameters of the Weibull distribution, also the dispersion in direction of the Number of cycles to failure can be employed, $\sigma_{a,ref}$ and $b_{\sigma,ref}$ can be calculated afterwards, using the S-N curve acc. to Basquin, Equation 2. Supposing, the reference Volume V_{ref} contains a number of n infinitesimal small and therefore homogeneously loaded Volume Elements dV . The differential expression, Equation 3, describes the survival probability depending on the survival probability of the reference Volume V_{ref} and the local stress field $\sigma_a(x,y,z)$ for a fixed number of cycles to failure.

$$P_{s,V_{ref}} = e^{-\left(\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_{a,ref}}\right)^{b_{\sigma,ref}}} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{s,V_{ref}} = e^{-\left(\frac{N_f}{N_{f,ref}}\right)^{b_{N,ref}}}, \text{ with } b_N = \frac{b_{\sigma}}{k} \quad (2)$$

k: slope of the S-N curve acc. to Basquin

$$P_{s,V} = e^{-\int_V \frac{1}{V_{ref}} \left(\frac{\sigma_a(x,y,z)}{\sigma_{a,ref}}\right)^{b_{\sigma,ref}} dV} \quad (3)$$

For homogenous property distributions, Equation 3 delivers the survival properties for arbitrary stress fields $\sigma_a(x,y,z)$. Because $\sigma_{a,ref}$, V_{ref} , and $b_{\sigma,ref}$ do not depend on the location x , y , z , it is possible to solve simple problems like a unnotched bar under bending analytical. Especially for cast components with additional heat treatment, the material properties depend significantly on the individual local process gradients and are therefore inhomogeneous. Assuming constant cyclic material properties will lead to inaccurate results and may cause either over or under dimensioning of the component. In order to exploit the full potential of the material, Equation 3 is modified, admitting a location and orientation dependence of the local material properties. It is now indicated, that $\sigma_{a,ref}$, $b_{\sigma,ref}$ and V_{ref} may depend on the location within the component, see Equation 4.

$$P_{s,V} = e^{-\int_V \frac{1}{V_{ref}(x,y,z)} \left(\frac{\sigma_a(x,y,z)}{\sigma_{a,ref}(x,y,z)}\right)^{b_{\sigma,ref}(x,y,z)} dV} \quad (4)$$

In order to apply Equation 4 to load and process simulation FEA, it has to be discretised and linked to the element volume in order to be numerically solvable. Assuming a sufficiently high element resolution it is admissible to neglect variations of the stress over the element and calculate with averaged results for the element centre. The reference values for the local fatigue properties as well as the cyclic material behaviour have to be mapped to the element centre coordinates, x , y and z .

$$P_{s,V} = e^{-\sum_1^n V_{elem} \frac{1}{V_{ref}(x,y,z)} \left(\frac{\sigma_a(x,y,z)}{\sigma_{a,ref}(x,y,z)}\right)^{b_{\sigma,ref}(x,y,z)}} \quad (5)$$

The result of the numerical integration of the volume integrals over the local stress and property field yields a survival probability for a constant number of cycles to failure and a defined local maximum stress. Depending on the calculation task it is possible either to evaluate a size effect correction of the number of cycles to failure, Equation 6, or the admissible local maximum stress for the fixed number of cycles to failure, Equation 7, also enabling a corrected calculation of the degree of utilisation, Equation 8.

$$N_{V,sc} = N_{ref} \left(\sqrt[b_N]{P_{s,V}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{a,sc} = \sigma_{a,ref} \left(\frac{b_\sigma \sqrt{P_{s,v}}}{\sigma_{a,ref}} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$util_{\sigma_{a,sc}} = \frac{1}{b_\sigma \sqrt{P_{s,v}}} \quad (8)$$

NUMERICAL MODELLING AND VALIDATION

Generally, the evaluation of integrals over the elements could be executed by Gaussian quadrature. Despite the reduction in required element size, this procedure is cumbersome and also not efficient, if solutions from different FE programs have to be mapped onto each other. It is therefore recommended to use the element centroid solution for the maximum principal stress in order to evaluate the stress integrals under the precondition, that the element size is sufficiently small.

Figure 9 shows the modelling approach for the consideration of locally inhomogeneous material behaviour and gradients in defect density. In the preprocessing, the local inhomogeneous stress-strain behaviour is applied to the component geometry together with the loads. After a non-linear static solution, the stress- / strain fields are superimposed with a matrix containing the local information for the strain-life / stress-life relation and the parameters for the modified weakest link approach.

FIGURE 9 Numerical modelling approach for the derivation of volume integrals and consideration of size effects

Figure 10 shows the comparison of the proposed approach with fatigue data from component release testing, a fatigue life estimation with a load based S-N curve, the results of a calculation with local material behaviour (strain-life) and the results with an application of the proposed modified weakest link approach. The diagram plots the normalised load amplitude vs. the number of cycles to failure.

All of the calculation results provide a conservative fatigue life estimation, taking into account, that the numerical calculations refer to a survival probability of 50% for the load-based linear-elastic approach and 36.8% for the strain-based fatigue concept with modified weakest link approach. The local approach without consideration of size effects underestimates the experimental fatigue life at the high load amplitude $L_N=1$ more drastically than the fatigue estimation with a load based S-N curve. At the lower load magnitude $L_N=0,75$ the local approach without consideration is already located nearer towards the experimental results. With the size effect correction by applying the modified weakest link approach, the numerically estimated fatigue life approximates the test results better than the fatigue estimation with the load-based linear elastic approach.

FIGURE 10 Validation of the proposed strain-life approach with modified Weakest Link approach

LIST OF SYMBOLS

- $b_{N,ref}$ shape parameter of the Weibull distribution of survival probability over the number of cycles to failure for a constant stress amplitude
- $b_{\sigma,ref}$ shape parameter of the Weibull distribution of survival probability over the stress amplitude for a constant number of cycles to failure
- k slope of the S-N curve acc. to Basquin
- N_f number of cycles to failure
- $N_{f,ref}$ number of cycles to failure for the reference specimen/component
- $N_{V,SC}$ estimated number of cycles to failure with modified Weakest Link Approach

$P_{s,V}$	probability of survival
$P_{s,V_{ref}}$	probability of survival for reference specimen/component
$P_{s,V}$	probability of survival for arbitrary component
V_{ref}	reference Volume for the Weakest Link Approach
σ_a	stress amplitude
$\sigma_a(x, y, z)$	stress field in the component
$\sigma_{a,ref}$	reference stress amplitude at $P_s=36.8\%$ (characteristic value of the Weibull distribution)
$\sigma_{a,sc}$	admissible stress amplitude calculated with modified Weakest Link Approach

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Scurria, M., and Wagener, R., and Möller, B., and Emre, S., *SAE Int. J. Eng.*, Vol. 10, No. 2, 2017, pp. 366-372.
- (2) Ramamurty Raju, P., Satyanarayana, B., Ramji, K., Suresh Babu, K., *Eng. Fail. Anal.*, Vol. 14, 2007, pp. 791-800
- (3) Wang, L., Chen, Y., Wang, C., Wang, Q., *J. Mech. Eng.*, Vol. 57, 2011, pp. 31-39
- (4) Li, P., Maijer, D.M., Lindley, T.C., Lee, P.D., *Mat. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 460-461, 2007, pp. 20-30
- (5) Nourian-Avval, A., Fatemi, A., *Mat. Tod. Communic.*, Vol. 25, 2020, Publ. No. 101567
- (6) Nourian-Avval, A., Fatemi, A., *Materials*, Vol. 13, 2020, Publ. No. 3068
- (7) Kloos, K.-H., *VDI-Berichte*, Vol. 286, 1976, pp. 63-76
- (8) Houria M.I., Nadot, Y., Fathallah, R., Roy, M., Maijer, D., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 80, 2015, pp. 90-102
- (9) Dash, S.S., Daolun, C., *Metals*, 2023, Paper no. 609
- (10) Nasr, A., Hassine, W., Maroua, S., Bouraoui, C., *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Tech.*, Vol. 98, 2018, pp. 2579-2589
- (11) Weibull, W., *A Statistical Theory of the Strength of Metals*, Ingeniörvetenskapsakademien Handlingar, 1939
- (12) Freudenthal, A.M., Gumbel, E.J., *Proc. Royal Soc.*, Vol. A 126, 1953, pp. 309-332.
- (13) Böhm, J., Heckel, K., *Z. f. Werkstofftechnik*, Vol. 13, 1982, 120-128